

1 Reclaiming the Matrix: The Importance of the Social Environment in 2 Psychedelic-Assisted Therapy

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13 Abstract

14 This paper recovers and rehabilitates early psychedelic researcher Betty Eisner's concept of
15 the "matrix" - the social and environmental context from which psychedelic therapy patients
16 come and to which they return. While contemporary psychedelic-assisted therapy (P-AT)
17 attends to psychological "set" and therapeutic "setting" as extrapharmacological
18 determinants of outcomes, this third environmental factor has been conspicuously absent
19 from modern discourse, despite contemporary understanding of neuroscience and
20 psychology providing compelling theoretical rationale for its salience to therapeutic
21 outcomes.

22 We argue that the matrix warrants systematic investigation for three reasons. First,
23 psychedelic-induced neuroplasticity creates periods of heightened environmental sensitivity,
24 during which post-treatment social contexts may be particularly consequential, especially
25 when complications arise. Second, established research on social support and mental health
26 outcomes provides robust grounding for expecting social-environmental influences on
27 therapeutic trajectories. Third, converging signals from clinical observation and qualitative
28 research suggest that P-AT patients with supportive, prepared matrices demonstrate greater
29 resilience during integration, while those facing social isolation or dismissive relationships
30 find challenging experiences more destabilising.

31 Recovering the matrix concept offers a quality improvement opportunity for contemporary
32 practice, potentially informing approaches to outcome durability, post-treatment care, and
33 treatment equity. We propose that validated instruments assessing social support, family
34 functioning, and structural resources be incorporated into research protocols: not for
35 exclusionary screening, but to identify patients who might benefit from enhanced preparation
36 and support. We outline specific measurement approaches and key research questions.
37 Unlike Eisner's original implementation, which was coercive and harmful, the practical
38 strategies we propose - support network psychoeducation, peer integration formats - are
39 time-limited, consensual, and autonomy-preserving.

40
41 **Key words:** psychedelic-assisted therapy; social environment; matrix; integration; social support;
42 extrapharmacological factors

43 Introduction

44 As psychedelic treatments for mental health disorders approach regulatory approval and wider
45 implementation, the field has made significant progress identifying factors that influence therapeutic
46 outcomes. Research has established the importance of dose (Goodwin et al., 2022), qualities of the acute
47 subjective experience (Kugel et al., 2025; Goodwin et al., 2025) as well as therapeutic alliance (Murphy
48 et al., 2022; Levin et al., 2024). Yet conspicuously absent from this growing evidence base is systematic
49 investigation of factors frequently predictive of outcomes across other mental health interventions: the
50 social, relational and environmental contexts in which patients live their daily lives.

51 Unlike conventional pharmacological treatments, psychedelic interventions explicitly acknowledge the
52 considerable influence of extrapharmacological factors on outcomes, a recognition that represents both
53 a strength and distinctive feature of the field.¹ However, this acknowledgment has primarily focused on
54 psychological "set" and immediate therapeutic "setting". In this article, we make a case for the
55 expansion of this acknowledgement to include patients' socio-ecological context, what early
56 psychedelic researcher Betty Eisner labelled the 'matrix'.

57 Introducing the concept of the matrix in a short communication, early LSD psychotherapist Betty Eisner
58 (1997) described the matrix as "that environment from which the subject comes, such as family and
59 living situation" and "the environment to which a patient returns after successful therapy—the everyday
60 living space." Her clinical rationale was straightforward: "if you change a person very fast and put them
61 back into the original environment, either the change is lost or they are under an enormous amount of
62 stress from the environment which created the problem in the first place" (Eisner, 1978, as cited in
63 Davidson, 2017, p. 89). Unlike the spatially and temporally bounded therapeutic *setting*, the matrix
64 encompasses the patient's family dynamics, social relationships, living situation, and community
65 supports: factors that exist beyond the clinical environment yet have the potential to exert significant
66 influence on treatment outcomes.

67 This emphasis on the importance of social, relational, and environmental factors to psychedelic
68 outcomes aligns with patterns seen in our own work, as an experienced psychedelic practitioner, patient
69 and participant advocate, and qualitative researcher. We observe that matrix factors appear relevant,
70 especially when complications arise, but also as mediators of optimal therapeutic outcomes. Patients
71 with prepared, flexible support systems demonstrate greater resilience in navigating post-treatment

¹ This recognition is now contested. Some treatment models approaching regulatory approval attribute efficacy primarily to the pharmacological agent, framing psychological accompaniment as serving safety rather than therapeutic functions (Goodwin et al., 2024). If the field moves in this direction, Eisner's "lost" concept may prove more salient in psychedelic science's future than it was in its past: where clinical support is minimised, patients rely more heavily on whatever their existing social environments provide.

72 integration, while those facing dismissive relationships, social isolation or material instability may
73 struggle to maintain gains despite profound acute experiences.

74 Eisner's own implementation of the matrix was fraught with serious ethical transgressions (see box 1;
75 Davidson and Plesa, 2025), and is one we emphatically reject. As such, in this article we seek to recover
76 (and rehabilitate) Eisner's insight about the matrix as a valuable consideration, demonstrating its
77 salience with reference to converging evidence from broader mental health research, theoretical
78 considerations about psychedelic action, and recurring patterns observed in P-AT practice.

79

Box 1. The Matrix Concept: Historical Roots and Ethical Reframing

The concept of the 'matrix' was developed by Betty Eisner (1997), a pioneer of early LSD psychotherapy who, with Sidney Cohen, published foundational work on the 'integrative experience' as a therapeutic goal (Eisner & Cohen, 1958). Eisner emphasised the importance of a supportive post-treatment environment for sustaining therapeutic change.

To realise this vision, Eisner established residential therapeutic communities where "patients would come from out of town for treatment and find lodging in one of [the] 'communes'...and were allowed to stay as long as necessary" (Eisner, 1997, p. 215). These eventually encompassed four houses and an apartment complex housing up to 40 clients and their families (Davidson, 2017). However, what began as environmental support became excessive control: dictating living arrangements, relationships, and personal decisions; secretly administering LSD; restraining clients for days at a time; and fostering coercive group dynamics (Davidson, 2017, The Cult Vault, 2023). Following a patient death in 1976 and subsequent investigation, her clinical licence was permanently revoked in 1978 (Davidson and Plesa, 2025).

While Eisner's therapeutic communities were ethically transgressive, her core insight - that post-psychedelic treatment environments shape long-term outcomes - finds contemporary support in neuroplasticity research and biopsychosocial models of mental health. This article recovers the matrix concept while fundamentally rejecting Eisner's implementation. Our proposed approach emphasises: time-limited engagement (bounded to weeks of enhanced neuroplasticity, not indefinite involvement); consensual psychoeducation (informing rather than directing); autonomy preservation (supporting rather than supplanting patient decision-making); and professional boundaries (resource provision, not life management). We argue that the matrix concept, properly constrained, offers a framework for understanding environmental influences without repeating the ethical failures that characterised its original implementation.

80

81 Conceptualising the matrix

82 Eisner's articulation of the matrix, while intuitively compelling, remains underdefined. While
83 descriptors like "family and living situation" and "everyday living space" are indicative, we are left
84 without systematic delineation of which environmental features matter (most), how they interact, or
85 where meaningful boundaries might lie. This conceptual imprecision is hardly unique to the matrix:
86 other foundational concepts in psychedelic science (e.g., 'integration', 'challenging experience', and
87 even 'setting' itself) likewise remain contested and lacking clear operationalisation despite their

88 ubiquitous use. While this state of affairs is far from ideal, it need not be fatal to the matrix concept's
89 utility. Rather, it suggests that empirical investigation and conceptual refinement must proceed in
90 parallel, allowing data to progressively sharpen our understanding of which matrix factors prove most
91 consequential.

92 Where Eisner emphasised the interpersonal dimensions of the matrix, sociologist Logan Neitzke-Spruill
93 (2022) offered a welcome extension of the concept by acknowledging that structural constraints can
94 create 'situational vulnerabilities' within patients' matrices: 'Phenomena such as discrimination,
95 victimization, opportunity for gainful employment, family ties, and social networks all constitute
96 situational vulnerabilities in an individual's matrix' (p.222). As well as enriching the concept of the
97 matrix by incorporating structural dimensions, this broader conceptualisation recognises that matrices
98 are multidimensional rather than uniformly beneficial or adverse—they may provide strong emotional
99 support yet limited material security, or offer stability while resisting change. Understanding how
100 different environmental aspects interact with treatment effects requires attention to both interpersonal
101 and structural dimensions of patients' social-ecological contexts.

102 A more fundamental challenge concerns the matrix's potentially limitless scope. At its widest possible
103 scope, the matrix could encompass nearly everything beyond the immediate therapeutic encounter: from
104 intimate relationships to cultural zeitgeists, from housing conditions to political climates. Such
105 conceptual sprawl threatens to render the matrix empirically intractable: if everything is potentially
106 relevant, how can we identify what actually matters? One productive approach draws on
107 Bronfenbrenner's (1979) ecological systems theory (EST), which provides a principled framework for
108 organising environmental influences across nested, interactive levels: the microsystem (immediate
109 settings like family and close relationships), the mesosystem (connections between these settings), and
110 broader exo- and macrosystems (e.g., community resources and cultural contexts). In line with our own
111 observations of patients and their support systems following P-AT, Bronfenbrenner emphasised that
112 these influences are bidirectional: individuals can actively shape their environments just as their
113 environments shape them.

114 DellaCrosse et al. (2024) have recently made a compelling case for applying EST to psychedelic
115 research more broadly, arguing that EST can help make explicit the "proximal and distal set and setting
116 factors" that influence acute psychedelic effects and provide structure for testable hypotheses about
117 contextual influences. While their participant-centered EST model focuses primarily on factors
118 influencing the acute psychedelic experience itself, our focus here extends this ecological thinking
119 specifically to the post-treatment environment and integration period.

120 To understand why the matrix warrants systematic attention in P-AT, we now turn to theoretical and
121 empirical considerations outside of psychedelic contexts that support the importance of socio-ecological

122 factors, before introducing converging findings from psychedelic research and practice that point
123 towards similar environmental influences in P-AT. Recent complementary work in medical sociology
124 has begun developing frameworks for understanding how macro-structural factors may condition
125 psychedelic outcomes at the population level (Viña, 2025). Our focus here, while acknowledging these
126 structural dimensions (cf. Neitzke-Spruill, 2022), centres on the more proximal microsystem level: a
127 patient's immediate family and close relationships. These represent both a tractable entry point for
128 systematic investigation and the factors most amenable to preparation and support interventions within
129 existing clinical frameworks.

130 Non-Psychedelic Foundations for Matrix

131 Significance in P-AT

132 Biopsychosocial Foundations

133 Before turning to why socio-environmental factors may be particularly relevant to outcomes in P-AT,
134 it is valuable to outline their role in mental health more broadly. The biopsychosocial model of
135 psychopathology (Engel, 1977, 1980; Bolton, 2023) provides a robust theoretical foundation for this
136 understanding. This model emphasises that mental health conditions emerge from, and are maintained
137 by, the dynamic interaction between biological, psychological and social factors, rather than arising
138 from, or being understandable in terms of any single domain in isolation.

139 That socio-environmental factors play at least some role in mental health is widely accepted, even
140 among those who criticise the biopsychosocial model. However, acknowledging social influence and
141 understanding its specific mechanisms are distinct endeavours. Social environmental factors can,
142 through multiple well-established pathways, directly influence the psychological and biological
143 processes involved in mental health, making environmental considerations more than incidental
144 background conditions.

145 The mechanisms through which social environments influence mental health outcomes span multiple
146 levels of analysis, from intrapersonal psychological processes to interpersonal dynamics and
147 physiological responses (see table 1.).

148 [table here]

149 These pathways demonstrate that social environments exert influence through processes (emotion
150 regulation, stress response, cognitive appraisal, behavioural reinforcement) that are centrally implicated
151 in mental health and illness. Rather than simply providing the context for psychological functioning,

152 social environments actively shape the processes through which psychopathology develops, persists, or
153 resolves.

154 Social-environmental considerations are relevant across therapeutic contexts for both practical and
155 theoretical reasons. Many mental health conditions develop within specific social-environmental
156 circumstances that continue to influence symptom maintenance and recovery trajectories.
157 Understanding these contextual factors provides crucial information about both pathogenic processes
158 and potential sources of therapeutic support.

159 Social relationships can influence outcomes through the same core mechanisms targeted by clinical
160 interventions: emotion regulation, stress response, cognitive processes, and behavioural patterns. This
161 overlap suggests that therapeutic change occurs not in isolation from patients' daily social
162 environments, but in dynamic interaction with them. The biopsychosocial framework formalises this
163 understanding: sustainable therapeutic change requires attention to the social, relational contexts within
164 which biological and psychological processes unfold.

165 These established relationships between socio-environmental factors and mental health outcomes
166 provide a foundation for considering their role in P-AT. However, demonstrating that matrix factors
167 predict P-AT outcomes would merely replicate established patterns in a new context. A more
168 consequential direction of inquiry is whether an interaction exists: i.e., do socio-environmental factors
169 predict outcomes of P-AT more strongly than for other treatments? Understanding whether P-AT
170 amplifies, modifies, or introduces entirely new forms of social-environmental influence requires
171 examining the specific mechanisms through which psychedelics produce therapeutic change.

Factor	Pathways to Outcomes	Evidence
Perceived social support	The belief that support is available (distinct from support actually received) shapes cognitive appraisal of stressors as more manageable. Perceived availability attenuates anticipatory distress and frees cognitive resources for coping, even when support is never accessed.	Cohen & Wills, 1985; Wang et al., 2018; Lakey & Orehek, 2011; Dour et al., 2014
Intimate relationship quality	Satisfaction, conflict, and emotional climate within primary romantic relationships shape mental health through partners' role as co-regulators of affect. Chronic discord elevates stress exposure while eroding the relational resources needed to manage it.	Proulx et al., 2007; Whisman & Baucom, 2012; Kronmuller et al., 2011
Familial relational quality and expressed emotion	The emotional temperature of family environments, particularly criticism, hostility, and emotional overinvolvement, generates chronic stress through repeated negative interactions. Critical attitudes shape self-perception and create behavioural expectations that become self-fulfilling.	Ma et al., 2021; Hooley, 2007; Lindert et al., 2025; Guerrero-Muñoz et al, 2020; Lex, Hautzinger and Meyer, 2022.
Loneliness	The subjective discrepancy between desired and actual connection (distinct from objective isolation) triggers hypervigilance for social threat, biasing attention toward negative cues and generating withdrawal that perpetuates isolation.	Hawkley & Cacioppo, 2010; Erzen & Çikrikci, 2018; Mann et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2018
Adult attachment	Relatively stable orientations toward intimacy and separation shape how individuals access support. Attachment anxiety amplifies perceived rejection and drives reassurance-seeking that paradoxically strains relationships; avoidance limits help-seeking and emotional disclosure, reducing access to support during distress.	Mikulincer & Shaver, 2007; Zhang et al., 2022; Dagan et al., 2018; Zilcha-Mano et al., 2021
Physiological stress systems	Social relationships regulate biological stress responses through multiple pathways. Supportive relationships attenuate HPA axis reactivity and reduce systemic inflammation; chronic loneliness and social adversity upregulate proinflammatory gene expression. These pathways provide biological routes through which relational factors influence both mental and physical health.	Cacioppo et al., 2002; Smith et al., 2020; Cacioppo et al., 2015

Table 1. Social-environmental mechanisms with established influence on mental health outcomes, with representative evidence

1 Psychedelic-Specific Considerations: Enhanced Environmental 2 Sensitivity

3 While environmental factors influence outcomes across many mental health interventions, theoretical
4 considerations suggest they may be *particularly* salient in P-AT. The neuroplasticity window thought
5 to be opened by psychedelic treatments provides compelling rationale for suspecting amplified
6 environmental influence, while the distinctive nature of psychedelic experiences may introduce
7 additional context-specific mechanisms.

8 Psychedelics enhance neuroplasticity through multiple pathways (e.g., increased BDNF expression,
9 dendritic spine growth, and enhanced synaptic connectivity) that converge on heightened capacity for
10 experience-dependent neural reorganisation (Lukasiewicz et al., 2021; Agnorelli et al., 2025). During
11 acute effects, psychedelics appear to reduce confidence in high-level beliefs about self and world,
12 temporarily liberating mental processes from entrenched patterns—a phenomenon captured by the
13 REBUS model (Carhart-Harris & Friston, 2019). The acute effects of psychedelics are followed by a
14 *subacute* neurobiological legacy: for some weeks after administration, enhanced plasticity effectively
15 increases the gain on environmental signals: neural circuits that might otherwise resist modification
16 become transiently more malleable. As such, there is a window during which previously rigid patterns
17 of thought and behaviour remain more modifiable through experience (Calder & Hasler, 2023; Zeifman
18 et al., 2025). During this window—which may resemble developmental sensitive periods when
19 environmental input shapes neural organisation with particular potency (Caulfield et al., 2025; Nardou
20 et al., 2023)—the patient’s social and relational environment may exert outsized influence on what
21 patterns take hold.

22 Although it is typically framed as therapeutic, enhanced plasticity is valence-neutral: it facilitates
23 adaptive change and maladaptive learning alike, and can offer no resistance to environments that simply
24 reassert the status quo. The outcomes of enhanced plasticity depend on experiences during this sensitive
25 period. Exposure to supportive versus stressful contexts are liable to produce divergent outcomes
26 (Castrén, 2005; Brouwer and Carhart-Harris, 2021). Bremler and colleagues' (2023) analysis of
27 extended negative responses to psychedelic use identified stressful circumstances and lack of social
28 support as key risk factors, suggesting a "plasticity × context" interaction: enhanced plasticity combined
29 with adverse environments increases vulnerability to negative outcomes².

² The time-bounded nature of this enhanced sensitivity, approximately 2-6 weeks post-treatment (Calder & Hasler, 2022; Agnorelli et al., 2025), offers a natural boundary for matrix intervention. This temporal constraint distinguishes contemporary approaches from historical implementations: Eisner's indefinite therapeutic communes enabled open-ended control over clients' lives (Davidson & Plesa, 2025), whereas intervention

30 Importantly, the case for heightened environmental sensitivity need not rest entirely on neuroplasticity
31 mechanisms. Caulfield and colleagues (2025) propose that learning itself (rather than plasticity *per se*)
32 may be the unifying mechanism of psychedelic action, with psychedelics potentially reopening
33 developmental sensitive periods characterized by enhanced responsiveness to environmental input.
34 Whether framed in terms of synaptic plasticity, prediction-error updating, or sensitive-period learning,
35 these converging frameworks share a common implication: the post-treatment period represents a
36 window during which environmental context may be unusually consequential."

37 The theoretical pathway is thus: psychedelics induce a period of heightened environmental sensitivity
38 (whether through neuroplasticity, reopened sensitive periods, or altered learning dynamics) during
39 which matrix quality may more strongly mediate outcomes. However, understanding *how* this
40 sensitivity translates into differential outcomes requires articulating specific mediating pathways
41 through which environmental factors shape therapeutic trajectories.

42 The general mechanisms through which social environments can influence mental health (see table 1)
43 may well remain operative in P-AT, potentially amplified by enhanced neuroplasticity. However, the
44 distinctive nature of psychedelic treatments may also introduce mechanisms more specific to this
45 therapeutic context. First, *integration depth*: supportive matrices can enable more thorough processing
46 of insights. The extent to which experiences are meaningfully contextualised and incorporated into self-
47 understanding partly depends on having conversational partners who can engage with the material
48 without dismissiveness or pathologisation. Second, *behavioural consolidation*: environmental
49 reinforcement shapes whether new patterns of behaviour persist beyond initial motivation. Matrices that
50 recognise and support emergent changes facilitate their stabilisation, while those that resist or fail to
51 acknowledge shifts may undermine therapeutic momentum. Finally, *meaning-making*: particularly for
52 transpersonal or ontologically challenging content, access to frameworks, loved ones, and communities
53 that can hold such experience may shape whether they become sources of distress or transformation.

54 While this theoretical framework provides rationale for expecting matrix effects in P-AT, empirical
55 validation remains necessary. Even absent the specific plasticity-environment amplification
56 mechanism, however, the well-established role of environmental factors across mental health
57 interventions suggests matrix considerations warrant systematic investigation: it would be remarkable
58 if psychedelic treatments alone proved immune to social-environmental influences documented across
59 other therapeutic contexts. In what follows, we show that converging signals from both clinical
60 observation and research studies point toward relationships worth investigating.

bounded to the neuroplasticity window targets maximal environmental sensitivity while preventing therapeutic overreach.

61

62 Convergent Indicators Supporting Matrix

63 Investigation

64 Drawing from systematic clinical observation and research studies across multiple contexts, two
65 converging lines of evidence suggest that environmental factors are a significant influence on post-
66 psychedelic trajectories. Clinical pattern recognition across diverse treatment settings reveals
67 relationships between social and relational contexts and integration outcomes, particularly during
68 challenging periods. Research findings from naturalistic studies, retreat contexts, and clinical trials
69 consistently point to social support and *people who understand*, or *who want to understand*, as
70 significant positive influences. Together, these indicators point toward relationships that warrant
71 empirical investigation, regardless of the specific mechanisms through which environmental influences
72 operate.

73 Clinical Pattern Recognition

74 The clinical observations that follow draw from years of practice providing psychedelic therapies and
75 integration support (H.W.). While unable to establish causation, these observations provide hypothesis-
76 generating signals that, when considered alongside theoretical frameworks and evidence from adjacent
77 fields, suggest relationships worthy of empirical investigation.

78 Patients who enjoy positive family relationships, a stable home life, and adequate material security may
79 find it easier to sustain the momentum of psychedelic-related therapeutic processes and navigate post-
80 dosing distress, in part because these conditions can provide emotional containment, practical support,
81 and a sense of safety during the post-treatment period. These factors, however, exist along continua
82 rather than as fixed or idealized states, and are dynamically shaped through reciprocal interactions
83 between patients and their social and material environments. Other circumstances appear to complicate
84 post-treatment trajectories. Individuals navigating major life transitions (divorce, bereavement, legal
85 proceedings, job loss) face competing demands on the psychological resources that integration requires.
86 Material precarity (unstable housing, temporary accommodation, uncertain finances) can limit access
87 to privacy, consistency, and psychological safety that may support ongoing reflection and meaning-
88 making. Similarly, relational instability - housing contingent on an uncertain partnership, or
89 cohabitation with people who are unsympathetic to their mental health needs or who can be experienced
90 as hostile - can compound vulnerability during a period of heightened emotional sensitivity.

91 A distinct pattern involves patients with ostensibly robust social networks who nonetheless have no one
92 they can share their experience with. Cultural or religious communities which disapprove of or prohibit
93 drug use can create a different kind of isolation: even during escalating distress, fear of judgment can
94 prevent them from talking about what they're going through. Such patients may be surrounded by
95 caring others, but nonetheless feel very alone with their experience. If they do open up, they may
96 encounter interpretations that exacerbate, rather than contain distress.

97 Clinical observation also suggests that matrix factors can function as more than environmental contexts:
98 in certain cases, they can serve as clinical indicators themselves. Consider a patient experiencing
99 chronic social isolation: as well as creating integration challenges, such isolation often reflects relational
100 patterns - difficulties with trust, discomfort with vulnerability, disrupted capacity for connection - that
101 may themselves be central to the patient's psychological difficulties. In this sense, matrix assessment
102 can provide clinically meaningful information about a patient's internal world, not merely their external
103 circumstances. These relational patterns can manifest during treatment as amplified feelings of lack of
104 safety, paranoia, difficulty requesting help, resistance to therapeutic engagement, and tendencies toward
105 concealment of distress - suggesting that matrix assessment can sometimes serve an anticipatory
106 function: identifying relational patterns that may emerge during treatment, as well as providing some
107 diagnostic information.

108 Across diverse cases, matrix factors seem most consequential during challenging post-treatment
109 periods, a pattern consistent with stress-buffering models from broader mental health research which
110 suggest that social support primarily influences health outcomes during times of stress rather than
111 providing consistent benefits (Cohen and Wills, 1985). When patients experience challenging drug
112 administration sessions or unexpected complications post-dosing, environmental resources become
113 crucial mediators of outcome trajectories. A patient returning from a difficult experience to a prepared,
114 understanding family, partner or friend who can normalise temporary emotional disturbances is liable
115 to navigate challenges very differently than one returning to isolation or to family members or friends
116 who are less able to provide emotional containment, or who interpret difficulties as evidence that
117 psychedelic treatment was misguided or worse. Crucially, however, these patterns are neither
118 deterministic nor universal: some patients thrive despite challenging matrices, while others struggle
119 despite apparently supportive environments.

120 Clinical observation provides one vantage point on matrix dynamics; participant experience provides
121 another. The following account (box 2) from I.R., a participant in a psilocybin trial for depression,
122 illustrates the texture of navigating social context during integration.

123

Box 2. One Participant's Experience of Matrix Dynamics

The following reflection speaks to the experience of I.R. following P-AT treatment. It illustrates several matrix-related dynamics: the experience of returning to an existing social context after treatment, navigating others' responses to change, and the interplay between social feedback and internal experience.

I consider myself very lucky to have had the circumstances I had when I took part in my first clinical trial, taking psilocybin to treat my depression. I had a supportive partner and a circle of close friends (although I only told one of them pre-trial so it didn't create fear or affect my expectations). I had a secure home environment and was out of work due to my ongoing mental health issues, so telling my manager or colleagues was not an issue.

But some issues arose with people being used to me being my usual clipped and stifled self. My partner said, "You're a bit too happy, everything's a bit too wonderful."

I felt more connected to myself, others and nature. I did also worry I may be too over the top at times, enthusiastic, talkative, a bit too much. There was almost a guilt attached to it due to the comments others made of my new excitement and exuberance. But at that point I felt alive again, my depression and anxiety had lifted, I felt free. To some of my loved ones, I wasn't being myself, not the self they were used to. It's not that psychedelics had fundamentally changed who I was, it was that I felt more able to be myself than I ever had before. No more anxiously second-guessing my every word and action.

As my afterglow faded, and there was little focus on or resources available for integration, my depression and anxiety returned and I settled back more into my previous patterns and perhaps once again became more predictable to the loved ones who'd been used to me being muted and more introverted.

124 I.R.'s matrix was, by most criteria, a favourable one: supportive partner, close friends, stable home. His
125 account offers a window into what integration feels like within such a context: the decisions about
126 disclosure, the experience of post-treatment change, the small moments of social feedback, and the
127 interplay between internal experience and external response. We acknowledge that a single narrative
128 offers texture, rather than causal evidence. We now turn to wider research evidence about the matrix,
129 indicating how similar themes play out across populations and contexts.

130

131 Research findings across contexts

132 Research findings across different contexts offer suggestive convergence with these clinical
133 observations, though without studies explicitly designed to investigate matrix effects, this alignment
134 remains preliminary.

135 Research identifies challenges related to both the *availability* and *quality* of post-psychedelic social
136 support. Studies of retreat attendees report challenges navigating environmental 're-entry' following a
137 psychedelic experience: "there was definitely a disconnect when coming back home. It is hard to relate
138 to some people, especially those that have limited experience in altered states" (Cowley-Court et al.,

139 2023, p.212; cf. Lutkajtis and Evans, 2023). A distinct but related pattern was found in a trial of
140 psilocybin-assisted therapy for treatment-resistant depression, wherein patients "who did not have
141 strong support from family or friends described feeling vulnerable and alienated afterward" (Watts et
142 al., 2017, p.548).

143 But research also suggests what helps. The Challenging Psychedelic Experiences Project, investigating
144 extended difficulties following naturalistic psychedelic use (n=608), found that one-third of respondents
145 endorsed peer and community support as valuable coping strategies, "emphasizing the importance of
146 empathy and shared experience in the support process" (Robinson et al., 2024, p.9). The most frequently
147 endorsed features of helpful support were "talking and feeling heard by others, followed by acceptance
148 and validation and shared similar experiences" (p.4): features that peer networks are distinctively
149 positioned to offer. Notably, not all social support proved equal: one respondent noted that "support
150 from family and regular friends (non-psychedelic) was almost useless. I felt like I was existing in a
151 totally different terrain than 'normal' people" (p.9). These findings point toward peer support as a
152 resource that can supplement existing matrices - or provide what they cannot.

153 Qualitative research on psychedelic integration groups (Modlin et al., 2025) report that participants
154 sought the community offered by such groups to find validation and acceptance, and to meet with those
155 who had undergone similar experiences, "to help normalize their psychedelic experience, within an
156 explicitly accepting and supportive setting" (p.23).

157 One trial of psilocybin-assisted therapy in cancer-related anxiety patients reported more positive
158 outcomes: sharing experiences with loved ones often led to valued increases in family connection
159 (Belser et al., 2017). The contrast between these outcomes illustrates how related experiences produce
160 different trajectories depending on post-treatment social contexts.

161 Recent participant advocacy work reinforces these patterns from the perspective of those enrolled in
162 trials. A 2024 report gathering experiences across multiple UK clinical trials found that participants'
163 support networks played a "critical and potentially under-recognised role" in trial experiences (Beckley
164 Psytech & PsyPAN 2024). One participant described the challenge of "having had this insane
165 experience, which is life changing and people don't know how to respond to you, your own people,
166 your family." This challenge can be particularly acute when support networks are psychedelic naive. In
167 the words of another participant whose trial protocol incorporated support network preparation, that
168 preparation was "really a key element" and "enormously beneficial," suggesting that meaningful
169 attention to the matrix need not remain an unrealistic aspiration but can be practically implemented
170 within existing trial frameworks.

171 Suggestive population-level epidemiological data point in a similar direction: Viña (2026), analysing
172 data from the National Survey of Drug Use and Health, found that psychedelic-associated reductions in
173 distress were attenuated for those with caregiving burdens, and in some cases reversed for single
174 mothers: a pattern consistent with matrix-mediated constraint on therapeutic benefit.

175 Taken together, these findings point toward matrix factors as meaningful influences, though the
176 evidence remains correlational. Although conclusive data in P-AT contexts are not yet available, it
177 would hardly be surprising to discover that supportive environments generally facilitate better outcomes
178 than adverse ones. A more interesting, and less obvious question (and one with direct intervention
179 implications) is *through which mechanisms* environmental factors shape outcomes in psychedelic
180 contexts. E.g., if matrix effects operate primarily through facilitating insight processing, support should
181 focus on psychoeducating networks to engage with psychedelic content. If through stress-buffering,
182 resources should target crisis support during difficult periods. Understanding mechanisms enables
183 appropriately targeted interventions rather than generic "improve social support" recommendations that
184 may waste resources addressing less consequential pathways. Understanding mechanisms enables
185 appropriately targeted interventions and clarifies *when* and *for whom* matrix support proves most
186 consequential, rather than implementing resource-intensive approaches whose active ingredients remain
187 unclear.

188 Operationalising Matrix research - measurement 189 approaches and research agenda

190 Matrix assessment in P-AT research and practice should identify prospective patients who could
191 most benefit from additional support, rather than functioning as a screening tool for exclusion.
192 Some P-AT trials already attend to participant matrices informally: therapists routinely inquire
193 about social support networks, housing stability, significant life events, and psychosocial
194 circumstances during screening and preparation. When participants disclose concerning situations:
195 accommodation instability (e.g., sofa-surfing) or recent housing loss, profound social isolation, or
196 the absence of anyone trusted to discuss post-dosing experiences, therapists may raise these with
197 the principal investigator and study team. Responses can include additional preparation sessions,
198 exploration of how contextual stressors may interact with integration, and enhanced post-dosing
199 support.

200 Such practices reflect genuine ethical attentiveness and participant safeguarding. However, their
201 informal and site-specific nature raises questions about consistency, transparency, and equity. How
202 matrix-related concerns are recognised, weighted, and addressed varies across sites, sponsors, and

203 trial designs, representing variation that is rarely captured in standardised documentation or
204 reported in publications. This limits what the field can learn. Without systematic measurement, we
205 cannot determine whether environmental factors explain meaningful variance in outcomes, which
206 matrix features matter most, or whether current informal practices are appropriately calibrated.
207 Moving from implicit clinical judgment to explicit assessment would enable the field to investigate
208 relationships that currently remain opaque, while ensuring that attention to contextual vulnerability
209 is consistent rather than contingent on site-level culture.

210 Fortunately, moving from implicit assessment to explicit measurement does not require developing
211 entirely novel constructs or instruments. The matrix relates to well-established domains (e.g., social
212 support, family functioning, structural resources) with validated measurement tools developed
213 across decades of mental health research. While a fully developed research program may eventually
214 generate psychedelic-specific instruments, currently available tools are sufficient to test basic
215 hypotheses about matrix influences on outcome variance. The challenge lies not in creating new
216 methods but in selecting and adapting existing instruments for psychedelic contexts while
217 addressing the matrix's multidimensional and dynamic nature.

218 Making matrix assessment explicit and systematic serves dual purposes: scientifically, it enables
219 researchers to investigate which environmental factors actually correlate with outcome variance,
220 improving generalisability of findings beyond the relatively privileged samples dominating current
221 research. Clinically and ethically, it can serve to identify patients who would benefit from
222 additional preparation and support during the critical integration period, ensuring equitable access
223 while optimising outcomes.

224 Matrix Measurement Tools

225 Initial research might productively focus on establishing whether matrix factors explain meaningful
226 variance in P-AT outcomes. Studies incorporating standardised measures of social support, family
227 functioning and structural barriers could determine whether these factors predict outcomes
228 independently of established variables like drug dose, therapeutic alliance, and dimensions of
229 subjective experience during acute drug effects. Demonstrating incremental prediction would
230 justify the additional assessment burden.

231
232 For interpersonal dimensions, validated instruments might include the Family Environment Scale
233 (FES), which measures social climates and relationships within the family; the Social Support
234 Questionnaire (SSQ), assessing both social support and satisfaction with that support; or the
235 Interpersonal Support Evaluation List (ISEL), which evaluates the perceived availability of social
236 support, including subscales for 'appraisal' and 'belonging'—factors identified as helpful in post-
237 psychedelic integration (Robinson et al., 2024).

238

239 For structural dimensions, assessments of individual material circumstances and social constraints
240 would complement interpersonal measures. Structured interviews and validated questionnaires
241 alike can assess concrete resource availability such as housing security, transportation access,
242 financial stability, and caregiving responsibilities. The Economic Hardship Questionnaire and
243 measures of material deprivation capture tangible resource constraints at the individual level. For
244 experienced discrimination and structural barriers, measures such as the Everyday Discrimination
245 Scale (EDS) and the Social Determinants of Health Questionnaire (SDH-Q) assess specific
246 obstacles that might impede integration of psychedelic experiences. In combination, such measures
247 acknowledge that matrices encompass both relational and material realities that influence
248 therapeutic trajectories.

249

250 A more resource-intensive but valuable approach for clinical practice would be the routine
251 inclusion of systemic psychological formulation at intake (Dallos and Stedmon, 2013; Jacobs and
252 Insua-Summerhays, 2025). In contrast to diagnosis, which involves categorising symptoms into
253 predefined disorders based on standardised criteria, formulation offers a personalised
254 understanding of an individual's psychological issues in the context of their life, history, and
255 relationships. Such formulations would systematically document both interpersonal supports and
256 challenges, as well as structural resources and constraints, identifying patients who might benefit
257 from additional preparation and support.

258

259 As with the introduction of any additional measurement instruments to in-human research, a key
260 methodological challenge involves balancing sufficiently informative assessment against practical
261 constraints. Cultural variations in family structures require instruments sensitive to diverse
262 contexts, while the matrix's dynamic nature suggests that single time-point assessments may miss
263 important changes. A pragmatic approach could begin with studies including brief, validated
264 measures of key dimensions, expanding assessment depth as foundational empirical relationships
265 are established, while incorporating longitudinal designs to capture changes over time.

266

267 If matrix factors prove influential, understanding *how* and *why* could inform preparation protocols,
268 support interventions, and outcome optimisation across applications of P-AT. We are not advocating
269 the pursuit of perfect environmental conditions for treatment—an impossible and ethically undesirable
270 standard that led to Eisner's coercive and harmful practices (Davidson & Plesa, 2025)—but time-
271 limited, consensual, autonomy-preserving attention to environmental factors during the period of
272 enhanced neuroplasticity that can improve therapeutic trajectories in ways that justify the additional
273 clinical investment.

274 Key Research Questions

275 With these measurement tools established, researchers can address several critical questions that
276 bridge theoretical possibilities with clinical reality:

277 1. Matrix as predictor: Do validated measures of social support and environmental stability
278 predict variance in 3-month outcomes beyond established predictors?

279 2. Matrix as risk modifier: Do matrix factors predict outcomes differentially depending on
280 whether patients experience challenging versus uncomplicated post-treatment courses?
281 Specifically, is outcome variance explained by matrix factors significantly larger among
282 patients who encounter difficulties than among those with smooth trajectories?

283 3. Matrix-informed support strategies: What preparation and support interventions during
284 the post-treatment sensitivity window can optimise outcomes for patients with challenging
285 matrices? How can temporary environmental scaffolding be provided without creating
286 access barriers or pathologising social adversity?

287 These questions arguably carry implications beyond matrix-informed care. The neuroplasticity
288 hypothesis predicts that psychedelics create a window of heightened environmental sensitivity. As such,
289 matrix quality should predict P-AT outcomes more strongly than it predicts outcomes in conventional
290 treatments not hypothesised to increase neuroplasticity. A null finding on this interaction would be a
291 prima facie challenge not only to the magnitude of practical salience of environmental considerations,
292 but also the clinical significance of psychedelic-induced neuroplasticity itself: if returning to adverse
293 circumstances after P-AT produces no worse outcomes than returning to them after conventional
294 treatment, the plasticity story thereby seems less compelling.

295 As such, pursuing these questions could clarify both theoretical foundations and clinical practice:
296 informing preparation protocols, support interventions, and outcome optimisation. Yet meaningful
297 progress on matrix-informed preparation need not await resolution of these research priorities; current
298 evidence already suggests practical steps that can be implemented within existing trial frameworks.
299 Before developing these, we first address practical and ethical concerns that matrix-informed
300 approaches naturally invite.

301

302 Addressing concerns

303 Proposals to systematically assess patients' social environments naturally invites concerns about
304 expanding clinical scope beyond practical or ethical limits. Three objections merit response.

305 The first concerns resource burden: matrix assessment could add complexity to already demanding
306 protocols. This burden falls on participants and patients themselves: those most likely to benefit from
307 enhanced support may also find additional assessment most taxing. We acknowledge this, but the
308 investment should be evaluated against potential benefits. If matrix factors influence outcomes as theory
309 and observation suggest, systematic attention may improve durability and prevent complications
310 requiring costlier intervention. Implementation can be incremental: beginning with brief, validated
311 measures at intake, expanding assessment depth only as foundational relationships between matrix
312 factors and outcomes are established.

313 The second concern involves overmedicalisation: framing poverty, discrimination or housing security
314 as ‘clinical risk factors’ risks pathologising structural injustice rather than addressing it. This tension is
315 real, and as one of us has argued elsewhere (Jacobs & Insua-Summerhays, 2025), adverse matrices
316 should not serve as exclusion criteria. Our approach assumes therapy occurs within existing social
317 realities while working to optimise outcomes within those constraints. Consistent with calls for equity-
318 oriented approaches that ensure fair outcomes in psychedelic services (Jacobs et al., 2024a; McGuire et
319 al., 2024), we argue that if certain contextual stressors can impair integration or exacerbate post-
320 treatment vulnerability, the equitable response is additional support, not gatekeeping access.

321 Finally, some may worry that emphasising environmental influence implies patients are passive
322 recipients of social forces rather than agents capable of reshaping their circumstances. But
323 acknowledging environmental influence need not negate agency. Clinical observation and research
324 interviews demonstrate that many patients actively restructure their matrices following P-AT:
325 renegotiating relationships, changing living situations, developing new connections. Matrix-informed
326 approaches should enhance autonomy by providing information about factors that might influence
327 trajectories, enabling more informed decisions about preparation and integration.

328 Practical Implementation

329 For researchers and clinicians who recognise the patterns described above, practical steps need not await
330 definitive evidence. The assessment approaches outlined earlier can identify interpersonal supports and
331 structural constraints that may influence post-treatment trajectories, while proactive preparation can
332 begin regardless of matrix quality.

333 Such preparation should occur *before* treatment commences, securing support network understanding
334 while patients are not yet in states of heightened sensitivity. This includes ensuring a support person is
335 identified, and offering psychoeducation addressing the nature of P-AT and common post-treatment
336 experiences. Preparation serves two distinct purposes. First, it can help supporters respond
337 proportionately to transient post-treatment difficulties (e.g., temporary emotional lability, sleep

338 disturbances, or periods of uncertainty) rather than catastrophising in ways that escalate manageable
339 challenges into crises. Second, it helps support networks understand that shifts in perspective, priorities,
340 or relational patterns may represent therapeutic progress rather than symptoms to be corrected, creating
341 space for patient-directed change. As the PsyPAN/Beckley Psytech (2024) report demonstrates, such
342 preparation is already being implemented in some trial contexts, with participants describing it as
343 "enormously beneficial."

344 Considering the qualities that have been found to be most helpful following psychedelic experiences
345 (feeling heard, acceptance, shared experience), peer support networks and group integration formats
346 (Modlin et al., 2025; Skiles et al., 2023; see also Cheung et al., 2024) represent a particularly promising
347 matrix-informed intervention. Unlike approaches that attempt to modify a patient's existing social
348 environment, such groups can compensate by offering supplementary matrix resources that do not
349 depend on family receptivity or existing relationship quality. Their scalability, especially relative to
350 individual integration therapy, speaks strongly in their favour given the overall high resource demands
351 of P-AT.

352 The theoretical rationale for such groups aligns closely with what Robinson et al. (2024) find helps
353 during challenging integration periods. That members may share not only familiarity with psychedelic
354 experiences, but also the broader circumstances of managing a chronic mental health condition (and, in
355 research contexts, the challenges of navigating a clinical trial) points toward something that
356 psychedelic-naïve family and supporters cannot provide, regardless of their goodwill: understanding
357 grounded in multiple layers of shared context. This compensatory function may become increasingly
358 critical as the field considers treatment models that minimise ongoing clinical contact. Where
359 professional support during integration is reduced in favour of scalability, patients must rely more
360 heavily on whatever resources their existing matrices provide. If the patterns described in this paper
361 prove robust, this displacement increases the importance of supplementary supports that do not depend
362 on existing relationship quality. Peer integration groups could serve this compensatory function,
363 offering structured resources for patients whose matrices are less equipped to support integration.
364 Offering such support as part of post-trial care, with systematic monitoring of uptake and outcomes,
365 can generate data on what works while meeting participant needs (Jacobs et al., 2024).

366

367 Conclusion: from measurement to understanding

368 The matrix offers a valuable framework for understanding how social and environmental contexts
369 influence P-AT outcomes. Through convergent theoretical considerations, clinical observations, and

370 research findings, we have demonstrated that patients' social environments warrant systematic
371 investigation as a quality improvement priority.

372 In this perspective we have highlighted three reasons justifying increased attention to matrix factors.
373 First, neuroplasticity research and biopsychosocial frameworks provide compelling rationale for
374 expecting environmental influences during periods of heightened sensitivity following psychedelic
375 administration. Second, clinical observations across diverse P-AT contexts signal how environmental
376 factors influence post-treatment trajectories. Third, research findings across naturalistic use, retreat
377 settings, and clinical trials consistently identify social support and environmental understanding as
378 influential factors in outcomes.

379 These convergent indicators suggest relationships between environmental factors and therapeutic
380 outcomes that merit empirical investigation. While it is clinically intuitive to anticipate that supportive
381 environments facilitate better outcomes than adverse ones, meaningfully impactful research would
382 determine which specific matrix factors matter most, for which patients, and during which treatment
383 phases.

384 By systematically investigating matrix effects, the P-AT field can develop comprehensive models of
385 therapeutic change that acknowledge individuals as embedded within social systems. Importantly,
386 matrix-informed approaches should enhance rather than restrict treatment access, providing scaffolding
387 for environmental challenges rather than creating barriers to care. Such an expanded understanding may
388 lead to enhanced outcomes, as well as more equitable access to those outcomes.

389 This investigation gains practical urgency as treatments approach approval under varying therapeutic
390 frameworks. Models that minimise clinical accompaniment during integration necessarily rely more
391 heavily on whatever resources patients' existing environments provide. Functions that might otherwise
392 be served by ongoing clinical contact: processing difficult material, reinforcing new patterns, or
393 normalising transient difficulties, must either be fulfilled by the matrix or remain unfulfilled.
394 Understanding which matrix factors support these functions, and how to bolster matrices that cannot,
395 becomes correspondingly more important as leaner treatment models are considered.

396 Though psychedelic therapies occur in controlled clinical settings, their outcomes unfold in the complex
397 social worlds that patients inhabit daily. Understanding the influence of those worlds represents both a
398 scientific opportunity and an ethical obligation as these treatments move toward widespread
399 implementation.

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